

STATIVE VERBS WHICH WERE USED IN “DEVONI LUG‘OTIT TURK”

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Abstract. In this article, some of the verbs of the state of action in the "Devoni lug'otit turk" were analyzed. And in order to clarify the dictionary meaning of these words in a wider way and to determine in what situations they were used in different periods, what changes occurred in the development of the meaning, "Alisher Navoiy asarlari tilining izohli lug'ati" and "O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati" was studied comparatively.

Keywords: vocabulary, verbs, state verbs, action verbs, object, subject.

Conditional verbs in the Uzbek language include certain processes related to nature and society, plants and animals, human biology, physiology and psyche, according to their objective basis. Therefore, verbs of situation differ from verb lexemes in other semantic fields by their breadth and complexity, "accommodation" of different situations specific to matter, according to their material basis (object). In the sense of state verbs, a realizable state is characterized by the fact that it occurs only within the framework of a certain logical subject, does not go beyond it, and remains in it. Status verbs express a state, someone (something) is in a certain state¹.

In verbs of state of action, state appears to be a permanent sign of action, its existence, a way of "living", but an incomplete, continuous sign. Because the disappearance of the state occurs with the end of the movement, that is, the movement exists as the source and basis of the state. In other words, the state of a logical subject is observed as an important feature characterizing a specific subject, together with action, as a whole². For example, in the work "Devonu lug'otit turk" the verb **öчур** - expresses the meaning of "to stop burning, to burn, to extinguish": *Анїң öнкäcїн öчурди* – He calmed his anger (DLT,I,186). In the works of Alisher Navoi, we find the following meanings of this lexeme:

1. So'nmoq, o'chmoq. *Va Ya'qub alayhissalomni muhlik motamg'a va o'chmas o'tqa soldilar.*

2. O'chmoq(uyqu).

El tilidin uyqu o'chmishtur ko'zimdin go'yiyo,

¹ Rasulov R. O'zbek tilida holat fe'llari va ularning obligator valiantliklari. Toshkent 1989. — B 19.

² Rasulov R. Yuqoridagi manba. — B 24.

Kim erur baxt uyqusining boisi afsonamiz (ANATIL,III,619). In the modern Uzbek literary language, the form of the studied word has been preserved and the following meanings are observed:

1. Yonishdan, yolqin berishdan to'xtamoq, so'nmoq. *O'tni kovlasang — o'chadi, Ko'shningni kovlasang — ko'chadi.*
2. Asl tusini yo'qotmoq, xiralashmoq, o'ngmoq. *Chitning rangi o'chibdi.*
3. Ko'zdan g'oyib bo'lmoq, ko'rinmay qolmoq, yo'qolmoq. *Gullar, yashilliklar orasida uning adil — kelishgan qomati, shaffof bir xayol kabi goh yalt etib ko'rinar, goh o'char edi.*
4. (Ko'chma) Yo'q bo'lmoq, yo'qolmoq. *Sahroning nomi o'char, O'zgaradi qumloqlar.*
5. To'xtamoq, tinmoq, eshitilmay qolmoq. *Hozirgina so'zlashib o'tirgan Kumush bilan onasining tovushlari o'chgan edi.*
6. (Ko'chma) Xotiradan ko'tarilmoq, esdan chiqmoq, unutilmoq. *Nomi o'chib ketgan Boqi mirzo ko'p vaqt o'tmay «inobatlik mirzo» nomi bilan bosh ko'tardi.*
7. Safdan yoki hisobdan chiqmoq. *Yozuvchilar uyushmasi a'zolidan o'chgan kishi (O'TIL,V,208).*

Mahmud Koshgari used the verb **афрп-** to express the meaning of "to increase in weight, to become heavier, to weigh down": *афрудї нѣң – thing became overweight. Iklik афрудї – the sick got worse. Афруп, афрумақ (DLT, I,186).* In "O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati" **оғир-** phonetic form of this word is used and it has different meanings:

1. Vazni, og'irligi oshmoq, og'irroq bo'lib qolmoq, og'ir tortmoq. *Yog'och bo'kib, ancha og'irlashdi.*
2. (Ko'chma) Tobora mashaqqatli bo'lmoq. *Botiralinig xayoli uning yelkasiga og'ir yuk bo'lib tushdi va bu yuk kundan kun og'irlashardi.*
3. Qiyinlashmoq, murakkablashmoq. *Ish og'irlashdi.*
4. Og'ir tortmoq, mushkullashmoq. *Bemorning nafas olishi og'irlashdi.*
5. Moddiy jihatdan nochor holga tushib qolmoq, mashaqqatli, uqubatli bo'lib qolmoq. *Ayam o'lgandan keyin ahvolimiz yana og'irlashdi.*
6. Noqulay, qiyin bo'lib qolmoq. *Endi qizining oldiga kirib, uning betiga qarash unga [qutidorga] juda ham og'irlashgan edi, chunki bu fojining bosh omili deb o'zini tanigan edi.*

7. Xavfli tus olmoq, xavfli, xatarli bo'lib qolmoq, jiddiylashmoq. *Ahvol borgan sari og'irlashdi. - Boylarning chaqirig'i bilan Io'lchining ishi og'irlashdi, - dedi Shokir ota.*

8. Kuchaymoq, zo'raymoq, tuzalishi mahol bo'lib qolmoq. *Bemor kundan kunga og'irlashyapti.*

9. Oshmoq, kuchaymoq. *Jinoyati og'irlashdi.*

10. (Ko'chma) Gangib qolmoq, o'zini yomon his etmoq. *Kishi dardini anglatolmasa og'irlashadi (O'TIL,III,210).*

In "Devoni lug'otit turk" the lexeme **kəwil** - is used in the meaning "to loosen, to weaken": *эр күчи кəwildi* – man's strength has weakened. The poem says:

Təgrä awıb oğrälim

Аттін түшүб жүгрälим

Арсланлају көкрälим

Күчи анің кəwilсүн.

Yon atrofini o'raylik, otdan tushib qattiq hamla qilaylik, arslonlarcha bo'kiraylik, dushman kuchi shundan bo'shshsin (DLT,II,159). This word fell out of use at that time, and today we use a number of lexemes instead:

1. Bo'shamoq. *Kuzda bolalar dala ishlaridan bo'shshsa, maktabni ochib yuborish niyatida edi.*

2. Yumshoq bo'lib qolmoq, yumsharmoq. *Yer yetilib, ancha bo'shshib qolibdi.*

3. Tarangligini yoki mustahkamligini yo'qotmoq, solqilanib qolmoq. *Stullarning oyoqlari bo'shshib qolibdi.*

4. Kuchi kesilib, pasaymoq, qaytmoq. *Shamol bo'shshdi.*

5. Madori qurimoq, jismonan zaiflashmoq,shalpaymoq. *Adolat bo'shshdi. Indamay, holsizlik bilan stulga o'tirdi.*

6. (Ko'chma) Hovuridan tushmoq, gapidan, niyatidan qaytmoq, bo'sh kela boshlamoq, hafsalasi pir bo'lmoq. *Oftob oyim erining keyingi so'zi bilan anchagina bo'shshdi.*

7. Bo'sh qo'yilganligi natijasida susayib ketmoq. *Intizom bo'shshmasin (O'TIL,I,530).*

Mahmud Koshgari used the word **бәртин-** in the meaning of "to weaken", which is a verb expressing the state of movement: *элик бәртинди* – the hand weakened. A weakness appeared in him, he became weak. *Бәртинүр, бәртинмак* (DLT,II,276). In the modern Uzbek literary language, this word is not used at all, and other words are actively used instead:

1. Sust bo'lib qolmoq, sekinlamoq, pasaymoq, susaymoq. *Sultonali bir oz sustlanib, o'zidan o'n ot odimi yiroqqa borgan tunqotarni chaqirib to'xtatdi.*

2. Tobora susayib, sekinlashmok, pasaymoq. *Ish sustlashdi.*

3. Bo'shashmoq. [U] *Intizomning sustlashib ketayotganini, bunga ba'zi komandirlarning o'zlari ibrat ko'rsatayotganlarini so'zladi* (O'TIL,III,676). The verb "susaymaq", which has the same sememe as the lexeme of "sustlashmaq", but differs in form as a result of a phonetic change, is also presented, in "Devoni lug'otit turk" this word appears in the **қуғшаш-** form: *кишиләр қамуғ қуғшашди* – people relaxed from the heat surrounding them and other similar circumstances. *Қуғшашур, қуғшашмақ* (DLT,II,405). The **күјфән-** form of this verb is also given: *эр ішқа күјфәнди* – the person slowed down at work *Күјфәнүр, күјфәнмак*. There is also a letter-changed form of this word in the style of *күфјәнди* (DLT,III,214). And Alisher Navoi uses the lexeme of **sustaymog'** in this sense:

Bu yo'l qatidin toymog'ing nedi

Ko'rub "Xamsa" sustaymog'ing nedi (ANATIL,III,132). There haven't any form of **қуғшаш-** and **қуғшаш-** in "O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati". These words disappeared at that time. Navoi's writings use the word "sustaymoq" to mean this, and this lexeme has also undergone a phonetic change to the present day and is given in the form of **sustaymog'**

1. Susaymoq. Sur'atning susayishi.

2. Keyinga ketish, tanazzul.

3. Ilgarigi kuchini, shiddatini yo'qotmoq, sekinlashmoq, pasaymoq. *Nusratbekning tashidagi titroq bir oz susaydi, sekin, vazmin, salmoq bilan odimlab ketdi.*

4. Shashtidan qaytmoq, ilgarigi g'ayratini, jo'shqinligini yoki qiziqishini yo'qotmoq, bo'shashmoq, pusmoq. [Kumush] *Kundan kunga Zaynabning susayib, o'ziga begonalashib borganini yaxshi anglar edi.*

5. Kuchini, ta'sirini yo'qotmoq, kuchsizlanmoq. *U [Hakimboyvachcha] yurtdagi tinchsizlikning sababini dinning susayganidan, ulamolarning xalqqa rahbarlik qilmaganidan ko'rdi.*

6. Bo'sh qo'yilganlik natijasida orqaga ketmoq, yomonlashmoq, pasaymoq, bo'shshmoq. *Intizom susaydi* (O'TIL,III,675). In "Devoni lug'otit turk", "the iron was heated" **тәмүр ісіді-** given that and to the heating of anything **ісір, ісімәк** verbs were used (DLT,III,270). Nowadays, lexemes expressing this meaning are used in their own sense and figurative sense:

1. Harorati ko'tarilmoq, baland bo'lmoq, isimoq(asosan havo harorati haqida). *Havo nihoyatda qizigan, otlar halloslab terlar.*
2. Biror narsa(olov va b.) ta'sirida tana harorati oshmoq, ko'tarilmoq (jism, tana haqida). *Badani qizidi. Tandir qizidi.*
3. Qizishmoq. [Sodiq:] *Qizib ketgan ekanman, qarang.*
4. (Ko'chma) Qizg'in tus olmoq. *Suhbat qizidi*(O'TIL,V,309).

Mahmud Koshgari expresses the meaning of "to increase" through **тәріңүклән:** *суw тәріңүкләнді* – the water deepened and increased. *Тәріңүкләнүр, тәріңүкләнмәк* (DLT,III,418). This word is also not used now, and we can find the words "to increase" meaning the lexeme **тәріңүклән-**, their meanings are as follows:

1. Son, miqdor jihatdan ortmoq, oshmoq. *Daromad ko'paydi. Chorva mollaring soni ko'paydi.*

2. O'zidan ko'p nasl qoldirmoq, urchimoq(O'TIL,II,259). In "Devoni lug'otit turk", "to rush" has become a synonym. In one place, we can find the verb **ашуқ-** expressing this meaning, and in another place we can see the verb **әwiш-**: *ол әwгә ашуқтi* – he hurried home or somewhere else. This word is also used for a person who is thirsty for everything. *Ашуқар, ашуқмақ* (DLT,I,199). *әwiшдi* – shoshilishdi. Example: *kiwilär iшқа әwiшдi* – people rushed to work. *Әwiшүр, әwiшмәк* (DLT,I,194).

In conclusion, we can say that with the passage of time, the meaning of lexemes expands. In the 11th century, one word meant one or two meanings, but by the time of Navoiy, these words were used in a wider range of places. Some words: **ашуқ-, очур-** word forms have been preserved even now, but most of the words used in "Devoni lug'otit turk" have fallen out of use already at that time. In the modern Uzbek literary language, we can see that some words are used in figurative meanings besides their original meaning. For example, the above-mentioned verbs "to heat up", "to relax", "to get heavier" and "to turn off" can be an example of this.

References:

- 1.Alisher Navoiy asarlari tilining izohli lug'ati. I tom.(1983). (539-bet). Toshkent.
- 2.Alisher Navoiy asarlari tilining izohli lug'ati. II tom.(1983). (539-bet). Toshkent.
- 3.Alisher Navoiy asarlari tilining izohli lug'ati. III tom.(1983). (261-532 bet). Toshkent.
- 4.Rasulov,R. (1989). O'zbek tilida holat fe'llari va ularning obligator valiantliklari.(24-bet).Toshkent.
- 5.Qoshg'ariy, M.(1960). Devoni lug'otit turk. I tom.(202-bet). Toshkent.
- 6.Qoshg'ariy, M.(1960). Devoni lug'otit turk. II tom.(167-141 bet). Toshkent.
- 7.O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. III tom.(182-bet). (2007). Toshkent.
- 8.O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. IV tom.(228-658 bet). (2007). Toshkent.